

The White Rock works site, Nant Llwynheiernin and the Kilvey Woodland, in Swansea 1737-2020.

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The industrial archaeology of White Rock copper works is well-known and thoroughly documented.¹ Looking at the site today, it is impossible to envisage the dense clusters of industrial buildings crammed into that bend of the Tawe.² White Rock's proximity to the slopes of Kilvey Hill meant that the Hill was profoundly affected by every activity in the works, whether it be water extraction, coal mining, smoke pollution, and most importantly, waste tipping. Outside of the Hafod chimneys, the most visible legacies of Swansea's copper industry nowadays are Kilvey's woodlands and the landscape scars that still lie beneath them.

In a pretty insightful section, the 2012 re-evaluation of the surviving Hafod ruins and their reinterpretation as a heritage park acknowledged the role of the 'icon' of Kilvey Hill and its regeneration as part of the industrial heritage of the wider area.³ Whereas earlier heritage plans would only have looked at the ruins (if any), a modern approach takes a more measured view of the surrounding landscape and climate change.

Conventionally, in the history of the White Rock site, much is made of its location, near a navigable river, easy access to coal, and engineered access to waterpower. Eventually, coal became doubly important as steam engines were first introduced to support the water-powered infrastructure and eventually replaced waterpower.⁴ Outside primary sources, the need for land for waste tipping is less often mentioned. Tipping is a vital part of the smelting process and a significant part of the White Rock story. The landscape we have today is the combination of a remarkable industry working for two centuries in a highly constrained geographical location. Aside from the industrial processes operating on the site, the physical location concentrated the adverse effects of smoke and waste pollution on the surrounding landscape, eventually resulting in the woodlands we have today.

Changing the focus and dropping the industrial remains out of the picture reveals some fascinating history and possibly lessons for the future. Despite the industrial devastation and the upheavals of the post-industrial phase, there are remarkable survivals of the eighteenth-century landscape which have escaped notice over the past decades. The early 1970s were a frenzy of remediation and Forestry Commission planting to hide the landscape scars. The bridge and road junction remodelling of the 1990s finally removed many surface features that survived. However, that is far from the end of the story; the history of Kilvey's environmental restoration and repair may be the best story of all.

Figure 1 An extract from the 1744 drawing of White Rock, usually attributed to an artist known in most sources as Thomas Lightfoot. The artist was viewing from Hafod on the west bank. The works are shown in detail on the right. Nestling amongst the trees centre-left is Ty Cnap Goch, the most prominent location on the valley's coal road. The Nant Llwynheini valley still has some vegetation, although there appear to be some dead trees.

The industrial development of the White Rock site was chronicled in the early 1980s, relying on the contents of two copy leases from 1736 and 1805.⁵ That earlier analysis of the copy leases understandably concentrates on developing the copper works itself, but a re-reading for landscape history gives some extra insights.

In the 1730s, the site was both occupied and busy. There was a rich agricultural salt marsh (Morfa Carw), a busy tramroad down to the Mansel coal yard (the original 'White Rock'), and a large watermill with a millpond. The mill was described as an 'old decayed or ruinous Water Corn Grist Mill called Knaploth Mill' (a corruption of Craig Cnap Coch or similar). The Knaploth Mill survived long enough to be included in a copy of a drawing of White Rock dated 1744 attributed to an unknown artist Thomas Lightfoot (or possibly Lighton) and shown as a substantial building in front of an impressive millpond, with a tantalising view of the main feeder stream and valley winding up Kilvey Hill.⁶ Sadly, the stream does not have a name that has survived. In my survey, I have called it Nant Llwynheini in reference to the area on the Hill near Llwynheini Farm and Coal Pits, where it originated before the substantial alterations to the stream structure in the 1740s. The drawing vividly illustrates the salt marsh fringing the river with grazing animals and the meadows behind. The artist has recorded the grassland and hedgerows being steadily submerged beneath the advancing piles of slag coming from the southern side. Ominously, the artist has even depicted a series of dead trees, likely casualties of the early pollution.

The critical part of the waterpower infrastructure for the early White Rock works was the channel or sluice into the Knaploth Millpond. It was also something that, once established, would be hard to alter. This last point may be why the Nant Llwynheini inlet into the White Rock site was (and still is) a permanent fixture. The sluice survives as it was built to carry the water under the Turnpike Road and onto the White Rock site. It currently has the much-reduced stream remnant under the Pentrechwyth road (the old Turnpike), the A4217, and the White Rock heritage site. Then, it travels south in various tunnels to run over the little aqueduct at the mouth of the Smiths Canal tunnel and into the river.

Figure 2 The surviving White Rock stream sluice originally fed the hammer pond and probably the millpond before the 1730s. The channel still survives, carrying the much-diminished stream under the B5444 and into the White Rock site.

Although the creation of more water channels and leats had a significant effect on the land, the tipping of industrial waste profoundly affected what we see today. Copper production was an unhealthy and toxic industry, transforming the landscape. The air pollution saga that dominated the civic affairs of Swansea in the 1820s and 1830s is nationally famous and comprehensively documented.⁷ More enduring are the physical waste piles the industry produced. Recent figures suggest that each tonne of copper in the 1730s could have generated approximately twenty-six tonnes of waste, although I constantly wonder if that is underestimated.⁸ The original White Rock site, as leased in 1735, was barely more than 2.4 hectares (6 acres), which left about two hectares (c. 4.5 acres) of adjoining fields and saltmarsh (known as Cae Morfa Carw) for tipping of smelting waste. The fields connected a larger enclosure to the north (Morfa Carw), which the Duke of Beaufort owned. This northern enclosure would eventually become Middle Bank Works. A lot of the land was only just above sea level, and the land adjoining the river was stone shoals, salt marsh, and pasture. The land surface we have today at White Rock is about 4m higher than the fields of Morfa Carw, but this is because the landscaping of the 1990s levelled out a lot of the small mountain of waste that marked the location of the original Cae Morfa Carw.

As early as 1802, the hill above White Rock was lifeless. The pollution on the dead hillside was sufficient to be mentioned by George Grant Francis in his 1881 celebration of the Swansea copper industry.⁹ This is surprising as Francis was keen to talk up the industry in a fine example of boosterism, but it may reflect the unavoidably ugly state of the hillside as it appeared to tourists of the early 1800s.¹⁰ Later in his book, Francis returns to the subject concerning Hafod being 'denuded of every vestige of verdure', with nature last 'having her sway' in the 1730s.¹¹

There was a notable change by the time the OS 1:500 plan had been compiled in the 1870s.¹² The plan shows that, via an inclined plane, tipping had spread over a large part of the lower reach of the Nant Llwynheirnin and must

have interfered with the leat and water channel system. However, the drainage sluice to the original Knap Goch Millpond remained open (as it does today). The waterpower system that had evolved since mediaeval times and powered the first one hundred years of copper production finally seemed to have lost its significance.

Figure 3 Leat 4 survives as a green oasis of biodiversity as it threads through the pines above White Rock.

The copper smoke devastated the ecology of the hill. Some sentiment of the loss experienced surfaces in the witness statements from the copper smoke trials of the 1830s. Morgan Morgan testified that Kilvey was now 'barren as a road, and the meadows of Hafod and Cae Morfa had all gone.'¹³ The OS 1:500 plan does indeed show horrifying extents of slag and waste in octopus-like tentacle shapes, reflecting the meandering of tram lines dumping successive layers of waste. The tithe apportionment from the 1840s confirms that John Freeman or subsequent companies had acquired most Kilvey farms east of White Rock. The lack of detail on the 1840s tithe plan suggests the surveyors found little interest in mapping there.¹⁴ The dead land would have been considered fit for nothing better than dumping.

By the 1870s, the Cae Morfa Carw marshes had been buried by a hectare of slag at least 4m in height and higher in parts. The riverside tip must have been physically incapable of taking any more waste by the 1820s, and it does not change its shape or size in successive OS maps and surveys until the 1960s. The extent of the 'secondary tip' across the turnpike and up to Cnap Goch House had spread to at least 8 ha by 1879. The inclined plane tram line running up the hill enabled easier tipping, and waste was spread up to and beyond the old house, which survived as a ruin surrounded by waste until the 1880s. The tip was busy, reflecting the fortunes of the White Rock Works, but by 1924 the works had closed with tipping ending shortly after, by which time the tip had expanded to about 12 ha.¹⁵ The tip continued to be worked and extracted as suitable ballast for roads and embankments until 1967.¹⁶

The polluting phase of White Rock lasted just over 188 years. The other industries of Hafod and Landore would grow and dwarf White Rock in the profits made and their negative environmental impact.¹⁷ Slag from the valley became a near-ubiquitous Swansea building and repair material. The slag tips are sometimes less recognised in the various histories of Swansea's industry.¹⁸ But just as industry had a profound effect on Swansea's history, the pollution left behind had (and still has) a profound effect on Swansea's geography.

Figure 4 White Rock and the Kilvey Hill area in February 1941. This is part of a series of bomb damage evaluation surveys conducted by the Luftwaffe across South Wales as part of the air war. The bomb damage assessor has identified in the white box the roofless ruins of the White Rock works as bomb damage (a common error). The white circles are craters of other bomb hits. The bend of the river is extreme left, and the dark land above the white square is the Cae Morfa Carw tip. The mass of the secondary tip is the centre-left, sprawling over the flank of Kilvey. I don't think there is a single tree identifiable in this view. To the right of the tip at the centre is the Nant Llwynheiernin valley showing signs of erosion because of the removal of protective vegetation due to the air pollution from the valley industries. The elaborate leat system is shown by the straight channels that cross the slopes collecting water and channelling it into the Nant Llwynheiernin. The industrial hamlet of Grenfell's Town is at the top.

Nowadays, the land that formed the White Rock tips is highly regarded as either part of the industrial heritage park (the original Cae Morfa Carw meadow) or the Kilvey Woodlands. Although the Cae Morfa Carw tip is currently only landscaped and grassed, the Kilvey tip has been transformed into vibrant woodland. A generation of outdoor enthusiasts is growing up using Kilvey woodland with little or no idea of the troubled past of the land. Indeed, it is sometimes hard to comprehend the area's industrial past in walking across the hill.

The earliest useful photographs of the tips come from July 1940, with later photos in February 1941. These photos are from the surveys of Swansea made by the German Air Force in preparation for bombing attacks (figure 4). One of the most striking features of this image is the almost complete lack of trees across western Kilvey, reflecting two centuries of atmospheric pollution from White Rock, Landore and Hafod. The lack of ground vegetation also shows the network of leats and watercourses created after 1740 to feed water into the Nant Llwynheiernin and onto the White Rock hammer pond. The secondary tip has covered the lower course of the Nant Llwynheiernin, and its cloaking effect over the topography is dramatic. However, the sluice that collected the Nant and channelled it into White Rock is clear of debris as it still is today.

The considerable efforts to remove the tips are part of the story of the Lower Swansea Valley Project.¹⁹ Although the main tip was geographically outside the project's scope, removing what was seen as one of the most visible tips in the valley was considered essential. By 1968 after about six months of work, tip material was either removed or regraded, and part of the Nant Llwynheiernin valley was reinstated.

The completion of the Lower Swansea Valley Project had a hugely beneficial impact on western Kilvey, and the restoration of woodlands in the 1970s and the later natural regeneration of vegetation are creating an environmental renaissance for the Hill. We will never recreate the original forest on the Hill; we have lost everything from that earlier time. Still, a combination of sensitive and thoughtful management from Swansea Council, NRW, and the local volunteer groups is creating a new type of urban Welsh woodland.

Figure 5 False colour digital terrain image of the present landscape. Nowadays, it is mostly obscured by tree planting. The original leat system has largely survived 1970s deep ploughing for tree planting.

¹ Stephen Hughes, *Copperopolis: Landscapes of the Early Modern Industrial Period in Swansea* (Aberystwyth: Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments of Wales., 2000), pp. 22–30; South West Wales Industrial Archaeology Society, *Industrial Archaeology Trail of the Lower Swansea Valley* (Swansea: Swansea City Council, 1975). The Trail pamphlet is fondly remembered by many walkers who used it to discover the Lower Swansea Valley for the first time.

² Stephen Hughes, p. 329.

³ Tehmina Goskar, 'Cu @ Swansea: An Industrious Future from an Industrial Past', p. 14

<https://www.academia.edu/1969069/Cu_at_Swansea_An_industrious_future_from_an_industrial_past> [accessed 27 November 2021].

⁴ 'Copy of Lease Dated 21 September 1805', 1805, p. 14, West Glamorgan Archives Service, DD Xhr 32. See for example the clause inserted into this lease to allow the construction of a steam engine to pump more water into the Knap Goch leat or Nant Llwynheiernin to supply the White Rock Battery.

⁵ R.O. Roberts, 'The White Rock Copper and Brass Works, near Swansea, 1736-1806', *Glamorgan Historian*, 12 (1981), 136–51.

⁶ George Grant Francis, *The Smelting of Copper in the Swansea District of South Wales from the Time of Elizabeth to the Present Day*, 2nd edn (London: Henry Southeran, 1881), p. 116; R.O. Roberts, p. 138. The origins of this drawing are obscure and it is possible that the version we see today is a copy from a now lost work. Thanks to Gerald Gabb for this extra information.

⁷ Ronald Rees, *King Copper: South Wales and the Copper Trade 1584-1895* (Cardiff: University of Wales Press, 2000), chaps 4 and 5.

⁸ John C. Symons, 'The Mining and Smelting of Copper in England and Wales, 1760-1820' (unpublished masters, Coventry University in collaboration with University College Worcester, 2003), p. 92 <https://doi.org/10/10._Bibliography.pdf>.

⁹ George Grant Francis, pp. 115–16.

¹⁰ David Boorman, *The Brighton of Wales* (Swansea: Swansea Little Theatre, 1986), p. 93.

¹¹ George Grant Francis, p. 139.

¹² Ordnance Survey of Wales. This series of plans at 1:500 scale covers the urban area of the town in the 1870s. Luckily, coverage extended to include mapping of the White Rock works and its waste tip

¹³ Ronald Rees, p. 78.

¹⁴ 'Welsh Tithe Maps - Home' <<https://places.library.wales/viewer/4570048>> [accessed 27 November 2021]. The Apportionment of the Rent-Charge in lieu of Tithes in the Parish of Lansamlet, White Rock Works, p.14

¹⁵ Nigel A. Robins, *Eye of the Eagle: The Luftwaffe Aerial Photographs of Swansea*, 1st edn (Swansea: Tawe History, 1993), fig. 6.

¹⁶ Borough Engineer, Surveyor and Planning Officer's Department, sec. 2.

¹⁷ *Dealing With Dereliction: The Redevelopment of the Lower Swansea Valley*, ed. by Rosemary D. F. Bromley and Graham Humphrys (Swansea: University College of Swansea, 1979), chaps 2 and 12.

¹⁸ D. Trevor Williams, *The Economic Development of Swansea and of the Swansea District to 1921*, Social and Economic Survey of Swansea and District, 4 (Swansea: University of Wales Press Board, 1940); Chris Evans and Louise Miskell. Are good examples of influential works.

¹⁹ *The Lower Swansea Valley Project*, ed. by K. J. Hilton (London: Longmans, 1967).